

Nickel Salts as Light Filters.

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It is well known that the addition of nickel oxide makes a glass very suitable for the transmission of *ultraviolet* rays and cutting of visible and infra-red radiations. Coblentz (*Bureau of Standards*, 1911, No. 7, 658) examined nickel chloride in search of a substance which absorbs all the infra-red rays. Emerson, Coblentz and Lang (*ibid.*, 1918, No. 325, 658) determined the transmission of a one cm. layer of nickel sulphate $\text{NiSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, nickel nitrate $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and nickel acetate $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_3\text{O}_2)_2$, the concentration in all cases being 10 g. of salt in 100 c.c. of water. Their results are summarised in the following table.

	$\lambda = \text{Wave-length in } \overset{\circ}{\text{A}} \text{ units. } \%T = \text{Percentage transmission.}$								
λ	... 6000	7000	8000	9000	10000	11000	12000	13000	
$\%T, \text{NiSO}_4$... 42	21	53	64	33	16	9	4.5	
$\%T, \text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2$... 42	11	50	64	33	15	8	4	
$\%T, \text{Ni}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_3\text{O}_2)_2$	25	10	35	46	23	10	4	2	

They have plotted the transmission curves. They are of interest in showing a sharp absorption bend at 0.7μ followed by complete opacity at 1.4μ caused by the absorption of water. None of these solutions were found to be as suitable as cupric chloride for absorbing infra-red. Solutions of nickel sulphate, potassium chromate and potassium permanganate are said to transmit the wave-length $6140\text{-}5760\overset{\circ}{\text{A}}$. Houstoun (*Proc. Roy. Soc. Edin.*, 1911, 31, 538, 547) has also investigated the absorption of nickel salts in visible, infra-red and ultraviolet for some concentrations but has not discussed their use as light filters.

The author has determined the absorption and percentage transmission of solutions of nickel chloride, nickel nitrate, nickel sulphate and nickel ammonium sulphate of various concentration. The method of measurement is the same as given in previous papers (Bhagwat and Dhar, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1931, 35, 2383) and the

concentration of nickel sulphate and nickel ammonium sulphate have been determined by estimating as sulphate.

Nickel Chloride.

λ = Wavelength in Å unit. M = Molar concentration. % T = Percentage transmission. e = Extinction coefficient.

$$\text{Normal solution} = N = \frac{\text{M. W. of nickel salt.}}{2}$$

(1) Concentration 4.63 N.

λ .	e .	% T .	λ .	e .	% T .
4000—4750	∞	0	5600	1.02	9.5
4800	2.0	1	5800	1.36	4.3
5000	1.04	9.1	6000	2.0	1
5200	0.77	16.9	6050	∞	0
5400	0.84	14.4	7000

(2) Concentration 4.63N.

λ .	e .	% T .	λ .	e .	% T .
000—4400	∞	0	5400	0.46	34.7
4500	1.50	3.1	5600	0.600	25.2
4600	1.08	8.3	5800	0.88	13.2
4800	0.58	26.3	6000	1.38	4.1
5000	0.37	42.7	6200	2.0	1
5200	0.40	39.8	6320—7000	∞	0

(3) Concentration 0.926N.

λ .	e .	% T .	λ .	e .	% T .
4400	0.48	33.1	5800	0.27	53.7
4600	0.21	61.7	6000	0.36	43.4
4800	0.23	58.9	6200	0.57	26.9
5000	0.16	69.2	6400	0.77	16.9
5200	0.16	69.2	6600	0.87	13.4
5400	0.18	66.1	7000	0.92	12.1
5600	0.22	60.3			

Thus the limit of transmission for these salts are as follows.

Concentration.	Range of transmission.	Maximum %T.
9.26N	4750—6050Å°	16.9
4.63	4400—6320	42.7
0.926	4000—7000	69.2

The results of absorption of nickel nitrate solutions of various concentrations have already been published. The limit of transmission for this salt are as given below.

Concentration.	Range of transmission.	Maximum %T.
4.16M	4400-6100 Å°	7.9
2.08	4300-6400 Å°	30.2
1.04	All visible	56.2
0.208	Do	91.2

It will be seen from these results that nickel chloride like cupric chloride absorbs highly at both the ends of visible spectrum. However it has got a very long range of transmission, even the most concentrated solution transmitting as long a region as 4750—6050Å°. It will also be clear that nickel chloride differs from nickel nitrate in that it does not obey Beer's law of absorption.

Infra-red absorption for nickel nitrate has been determined by Coblentz, Emerson and Lang (*loc. cit.*) for 10% solution. Assuming Beer's law, infra-red absorption for other concentrations examined by the author has been calculated.

Concentration 4.16M.				Concentration 2.08M.			
λ.	%T.	λ.	%T.	λ.	%T.	λ.	%T.
7000	0	11000	0	7000	0.04	11000	0.12
8000	0.67	12000	0	8000	8.30	12000	0.026
9000	3.98	13000	0	9000	10.2	13000	0
10000	0.037	14000	0	10000	1.99	14000	0

Nickel Sulphate.

(1) Concentration 5.28N.

λ .	e .	%T.	λ .	e .	%T.
6250	∞	0	5200	0.40	39.8
6200	2.35	0.44	5000	0.27	53.7
6000	1.65	2.2	4800	0.48	33.1
5800	1.85	9.1	4600	0.90	12.5
5600	0.65	22.3	4500	1.40	3.98
5400	0.50	31.6	4400	∞	0

(2) Concentration 2.3N.

λ .	e .	%T.	λ .	e .	%T.
6800	∞	0	5400	0.20	63.1
6600	1.85	1.4	5200	0.17	67.6
6400	1.70	1.9	5000	0.10	79.4
6200	1.25	5.6	4800	0.17	67.6
6000	0.70	19.9	4600	0.32	47.8
5800	0.42	38.1	4400	0.83	14.7
5600	0.30	50.1			

(3) Concentration 0.93N.

λ .	e .	%T.	λ .	e .	%T.
7000	—	—	5400	0.10	79.4
6600	0.85	14.1	5200	0.08	83.1
6400	0.70	19.9	5000	0.05	89.1
6200	0.55	28.1	4800	0.08	83.1
6000	0.30	50.1	4600	0.10	79.4
5800	0.17	67.6	4400	0.22	60.2
5600	0.15	72.4			

Thus the limits of transmission for nickel sulphate are as given below.

Concentration.	Range of transmission.	Maximum % T.
5.28N	4400-6200 Å	53.7
2.3	4000-6800	79.4
0.93	All	89.1

Nickel Ammonium Sulphate.

λ .	e .	% T.	λ .	e .	% T.
7200	∞	0	5800	0.59	25.7
6400	1.60	2.5	5600	0.44	36.3
6200	1.26	5.4	5200	0.37	42.6
6000	0.88	13.1	4700	0.58	26.3

From the study of these nickel salts it will be clear that all of them show a maximum transmission in the region 5000\AA . It is interesting to note that in case of nickel chloride the maximum transmission falls at 5200\AA . This is evident, because the absorption in dilute solution in the case of the nickel salts is mainly due to common nickelous ions, but in case of nickel chloride, the anion also exerts its influence, especially in concentrated solutions, where the absorption is mainly due to nickel chloride molecule. We know that chlorine has absorption towards violet and hence the maxima for the transmission is shifted towards longer wave-length. When the solution becomes dilute even nickel chloride shows maximum transmission at 5000\AA .

The ultraviolet transmission for nickel nitrate has been determined photographically and is recorded below.

Conc. (M)	...	4.16	2.08	1.04	0.416	0.208	0.020
Range of transmission (\AA)		3327-3427	3307-3598	3248-3598	324-3860 and	2618-3860	2442 above

Thus nickel nitrate has absorption maxima in the region, $3860-4023\text{\AA}$ in the ultra violet.

The author (Bhagwat, *U.P. Acad. Sciences*, 1932, 2, 67) has already discussed the use of nickel salts as light filters in combination with cobalt salts and have shown that these combinations transmit purely the ultraviolet region and hence are most suitable light filters for ultraviolet transmission. A short summary of these ultraviolet light filters is given below.

Ultraviolet and Visible Transmission.

Salt.	Time of exposure.	Visible.	Ultraviolet.
(1) $2.08M\text{-Ni(NO}_3)_2 + 1.83M\text{-CoCl}_2$, each in 1 cm. quarter cell	4 hr.	$5600-6300\text{\AA}$	$3307-3598\text{\AA}$
(2) $4.16M\text{-Ni(NO}_3)_2 + 3.66M\text{-CoCl}_2$	4	Nil	$3420-3527$ (faint)
(3) $2.08M\text{-Ni(NO}_3)_2 + 3.66M\text{-CoCl}_2$	4	Nil	$3307-3598$
(4) $3.66M\text{-CoCl}_2$	4	$7100-7600\text{\AA}$	$2618-4063$

Nickel Nitrate.

(1) Concentration 4.16M.

λ .	e .	%T.	λ .	e .	%T.
4400	∞ faint	0	5400	1.20	6.3
4450	∞	0	5600	1.25	5.6
4500	3.20	0.068	5800	1.95	1.1
4600	2.45	0.35	5900	2.65	0.22
4800	1.30	5.0	6000	4.45	0.001
5000	1.10	7.9	6050	faint	0
5200	1.17	6.7		∞	
			6100	∞	0

(2) Concentration 2.08M.

λ .	e .	%T.	λ .	e .	%T.
4300	∞	0	5600	0.60	25.1
4400	1.65	2.2	5800	0.96	10.9
4600	1.20	6.3	6000	1.70	1.99
4800	0.57	26.9	6200	3.0	0.10
5000	0.52	30.2	6300	3.8	0.016
5200	0.55	28.1	6400	∞	0
5400	0.57	26.9			

(3) Concentration 1.04M.

λ .	e .	%T.	λ .	e .	%T.
4400	0.82	15.1	5600	0.28	52.4
4600	0.55	28.2	5800	0.47	33.8
4800	0.30	50.0	6000	0.83	14.7
5000	0.25	56.2	6400	1.90	1.26
5200	0.27	53.7	6600	2.20	0.63
5400	0.27	53.7	7000	2.45	0.35

(4) Concentration 0.208M.

λ .	e .	%T.	λ .	e .	%T.
4400	0.16	69.1	5800	0.09	81.5
4600	0.10	79.4	6000	0.16	69.2
4800	0.06	87.1	6200	0.29	51.3
5000	0.04	91.2	6400	0.36	43.6
5200	0.05	89.1	6600	0.40	39.8
5400	0.05	89.1	7000	0.45	35.5
5600	0.05	89.1			

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